

Deep Learning-based Sentiment Analysis of Olympics Tweets

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Abstract—Sentiment analysis (SA), is an approach of natural language processing (NLP) for determining a text’s emotional tone by analyzing subjective information such as views, feelings, and attitudes toward specific topics, products, services, events, or experiences. This study tries to develop an advanced deep learning (DL) model for SA to understand global audience emotions through tweets in the context of the Olympic Games. The findings represent global attitudes around the Olympics and contribute to the advancement of SA models. We have used NLP for tweet preprocessing and sophisticated DL models for performing SA. This research enhances the reliability and accuracy of sentiment classification. The study focuses on data selection, preprocessing, visualization, feature extraction, and model building, featuring a baseline Naïve Bayes (NB) model and three advanced DL models: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM), and Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT). The results of the experiments show that the BERT model can efficiently classify sentiments related to the Olympics, achieving the highest accuracy of 99.23

Index Terms—sentiment analysis, deep learning, twitter, olympics, NB, CNN, BiLSTM, BERT

I. INTRODUCTION

The Olympics (French: Jeux olympiques) [1], a pinnacle of athletic excellence and international camaraderie, testify to the sport’s capacity to unite people globally. These respected events attract competitors and fans all over the world, breaking down geographical, cultural, and linguistic barriers. The advanced digital age has brought about a new era of involvement in the Olympics, with social media platforms acting as lively hubs of contact and conversations. There is a global upsurge of colloquialisms, dialogues, slangs, and viewpoints as social media sites like Twitter, Instagram, Reddit [2], and others come alive with debates, critiques, and sentimental statements about various aspects of the Olympic Games.

Twitter is a popular place where people can freely express their thoughts and emotions. The Olympics take place every 4 years. According to reports from the International Olympic Committee (IOC) [3], thousands of athletes compete in various games during the Winter and Summer Games. These competitions aim to promote global goodwill and highlight the limits of human potential rather than just medal competitions.

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The research does not endorse any particular nation or athlete but rather is based on social media discourse. There is a lack of studies on Olympic-related tweets, and those that do often suffer from low accuracy. There are many challenges in using Twitter data for SA and predicting actual public interest. To address these gaps, our study combines cultural studies and social sciences and uses NLP, DL, contextual embeddings, and robust feature extraction to improve accuracy and reliability.

As data and computing power have increased in the past few years, the field of artificial intelligence (AI) has seen a gradual increase in interest in DL, a branch of machine learning (ML), and it is based on artificial neural networks (ANN) [4] that draw inspiration from the function and structure of the brain. Models for DL that extract dynamics and features directly from the data can expedite the data preparation process and have a superior comprehension of intricate data patterns.

In essence, this paper aims to capture the global sentiment, reflected in Twitter data about the Olympics, using advanced DL models and shedding light on the complex aspects. We used a large dataset of tweets.

II. RELATED WORK

Several studies were undertaken to acquire expertise in evoking emotion through text. Before commencing this research, we focused on examining numerous significant varieties of studies to gather insights. In this paper [5], a total of 10,000 tweets were collected and trained for the Tokyo 2020 Olympics public health SA using an LSTM model [6]. The tweets had been classified as positive, negative, or neutral. The model’s sentiment classification final validation accuracy was 88.2%. Positive sentiments about public health during the Tokyo 2020 Olympics were 40.39%.

This study [7] presents a method for using SA to interpret news articles inside a multilingual corpus. It evaluates and combines SA algorithms to improve output quality. The study reviews the limits of the algorithms using SHAP and proposes using the 3 classifiers (Amazon BERT, Sent140 BERT, and Vader) [8] to identify contradictory results. An imbalance in the media’s coverage of the legacies of London 2012 and the Rio 2016 Olympics [9] is exposed by utilizing a dataset of 1271 articles in Portuguese and English from 7 media sites.

Due to data features like tweet length, spelling mistakes, and special characters, SA on social media platforms is a challenging task. This paper [10] proposes a CNN [4] model that outperforms baseline models. This article, London 2012 [11], suggests a combination method for analyzing major sporting events using social media data. It considers event days, user groups, SA, and topic extraction. The results reveal that diverse geographical and temporal patterns may be found, discriminating between residents and tourists and extracting issues about transportation infrastructure.

III. METHODOLOGY & EXPERIMENTS

We frame sentiment analysis using deep learning models as a supervised classification task. Our objective is to classify Olympics tweets, and that dataset was gathered from Kaggle (kaggle.com) [3]. Relevant features are extracted from the tweets for sentiment categorization, and deep learning methods are employed along with a baseline model, shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Sentiment Analysis Workflow

The SA Workflow: The workflow of the framework for SA is illustrated in Fig. 1, and it comprises the main seven phases of operation, i.e., choosing a good dataset, data preparation, cleaning, visualizations, feature extraction, model building, and presentation of the result.

A brief description of its phases is given below.

A. Dataset Selection and Preparation

It is an obvious fact that, in the realm of ML/DL, the acquisition of data is the initial and pivotal stage, with a profound understanding of datasets before the inception of ML/DL solutions. Data provides clarity and objectivity, so it results in better decisions. However, emotions and personal biases can cause tunnel vision, myopic perspectives, and costly mistakes. Raw data must be transformed into a usable format by making it more digestible, requiring a certain level of data literacy.

“Data beats emotions.” - S. Rad [12].

Dataset Selection: We carefully selected a dataset from Kaggle (kaggle.com), specifically tailored to encompass tweets related to the Olympics.

Sentiments (target) consideration: We separated the target variable and the features. In this case, the sentiment of the tweets was considered the target variable, while the tweet text served as the feature. For supervised learning models, this step is very crucial.

Label Encoding: To ease DL, we used label encoding to convert the categorical target variable into a numerical representation. Specifically, we encoded positive sentiments as 1 and negative sentiments as 0.

B. Data Loading and Cleaning

Data loading: For the BiLSTM [13] model, our 100% dataset is loaded at once. The dataset loading can also be done by loading the already separated `train_data` (90%) and `test_data` (10%), ensuring generalization to unseen data, used for our CNN and BERT [14] model. Proper loading and splitting help to build robust DL models.

Data Cleaning: Effective data cleaning is necessary to ensure the accuracy and reliability of DL models. This portion details the steps and methodologies used to transform raw, noisy data into a structured, analyzable format. First, to standardize text data, we handled contractions. A CSV file containing common contractions and their expanded forms was read into a DataFrame and converted into a dictionary. All entries were converted to lowercase for uniformity. Several regex patterns were used to identify and replace specific text elements, including URLs, @user mentions, hashtags, repeated characters, and emojis. Emojis, being key emotion indicators, were replaced with descriptive tokens. A custom function also converted tweets to lowercase, replaced URLs with `¡url¡`, mentions with `¡user¡`, reduced repeated characters, expanded contractions, removed non-alphanumeric characters, and spaced out slashes. More data cleaning steps included:

1. We took abbreviations and acronyms from the text and replaced them with their full forms, e.g., “LOL” was expanded to “laugh out loud.”
2. Words containing digits were converted to text format, e.g., “N8” was converted to “night.”
3. Common stop words, which do not add significant value to the text sentiment, were removed.
4. The lemmatization process reduced words to their root forms (lemma), e.g., “running” becomes “run,” enhancing the consistency of the text data.
5. A special phonetic algorithm was used to normalize words that had different spellings but the same pronunciation.

C. Tweet Deep Cleaning

Moreover, tweet deep cleaning also has been done. We created a column to display the cleaned text length so that we could see if we removed too much text or almost the entire tweet. We used the separately loaded datasets `train_data` and `text_data` for this visualization.

G. Model Building

Naïve Bayes (NB) [1], [18] was used as a baseline model and trained on TF-IDF features. This classical machine learning model served as a point of comparison for the more advanced deep learning models implemented in this study [19].

The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [4] model consisted of three convolutional layers. Each convolutional layer was followed by max pooling, which helped in downsampling the feature maps while retaining essential information. Dropout was used after pooling layers to reduce overfitting and enhance model generalization.

The Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) model architecture included an embedding layer followed by a convolutional layer to extract local features. This was followed by a bidirectional LSTM layer, which enabled the model to learn dependencies in both forward and backward directions. Dropout was added for regularization, and a softmax output layer was used for final sentiment classification.

The BERT model [14], [20] was fine-tuned using the Hugging Face Transformers library. It utilized input embeddings that combined token embeddings, segment embeddings, and positional embeddings. This configuration allowed BERT to understand the contextual meaning of words in the tweet dataset. The pre-trained `bert-base-uncased` model was used, and it was fine-tuned on the sentiment classification task with labeled tweet data.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Performance Metrics

The models were evaluated using standard metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. These metrics helped in understanding how well each model performed in classifying the sentiments of the tweets.

B. Model Evaluation

NB achieved an accuracy of 83%, serving as a baseline for comparison. The CNN model produced a significant improvement, reaching 98% accuracy. The BiLSTM model achieved an accuracy of 97.35%, demonstrating its effectiveness in capturing sequential dependencies. Among all models, the BERT model performed the best, achieving a test accuracy of 99.23%.

TABLE I
CLASSIFICATION REPORT FOR ALL MODELS

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
Naïve Bayes (NB)	0.81	0.84	0.82	83%
CNN	0.97	0.98	0.97	98%
BiLSTM	0.96	0.97	0.96	97.35%
BERT	0.99	0.99	0.99	99.23%

C. Model Comparison

The BERT model outperformed CNN, BiLSTM, and NB, showcasing its superior contextual understanding. The use of token, segment, and position embeddings helped BERT understand the structure and sentiment context more effectively. Learning curves for each model were also plotted to observe convergence trends and generalization performance across epochs.

Fig. 8. Comparison of Proposed Models

D. Error Cases and Challenges

Sentiment depends heavily on context, which often leads to misclassification. For example, the word "well" in the sentence "The old Olympic well is now dry" requires contextual understanding. Another example includes implicit sentiment expression, such as "Watching the marathon in the rain brought bittersweet memories," where emotional tone is not explicitly stated. Additionally, the loss of vocal and facial cues [2] in plain text presents a challenge in accurately interpreting sentiment from tweets.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that advanced deep learning models, particularly BERT, substantially improve the accuracy of sentiment analysis. The comprehensive approach involving data cleaning, visualization, feature extraction, and model building led to a test accuracy of 99.23% using the BERT model.

These findings support the effectiveness of BERT in robust and context-rich sentiment classification. In comparison to traditional and other deep learning models like Naïve Bayes, CNN, and BiLSTM, BERT showed a notable performance improvement. The study also provides insights into public opinion related to the Olympics, contributing valuable information for stakeholders interested in public sentiment trends on social media platforms.

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AVAILABILITY OF DATA

All data generated or analyzed during this study will be available on request.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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